

“To assess surgical outcome of mastoid cavity obliteration with postauricular soft tissue in canal wall down mastoidectomy”

Submitted by

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

S No.	ABBREVIATION	FULL FORM
1	%	Percentage
2	EAC	External auditory canal
3	TM	Tympanic Membrane
4	CSOM	Chronic suppurations otitis media
5	D/s	Discharge
6	POD	Post operative day
7	CWD	Canal wall down mastoidectomy
8	CSF	Cerebrospinal fluid

ABSTRACT

Introduction

Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media (CSOM) is a common ear condition in India and many other parts of the world. The incidence of CSOM is estimated at more than 20 million people worldwide. It is characterized by chronic middle ear and mastoid cavity inflammation, typically leading to persistent ear discharge and hearing loss. mastoid cavity obliteration with postauricular soft tissue in canal wall down (CWD) mastoidectomy is likely to see several advancements and refinements aimed at improving patient outcomes, surgical efficiency, and overall healthcare effectiveness, especially with Minimally Invasive Approaches.

Objectives

The objectives of the study were to evaluate the surgical outcomes of mastoid cavity obliteration using postauricular soft tissue in patients undergoing CWD mastoidectomy for CSOM with cholesteatoma.

Methods

The study was a hospital-based prospective study with a sample size of 48 subjects, divided into case and control groups. The primary outcome measure was the creation of a dry, infection-free, low-maintenance mastoid cavity as assessed by a grading system developed by Merchant et al.

The study used a cohort of patients undergoing CWDM for CSOM with cholesteatoma, with postauricular soft tissue used to obliterate the mastoid cavity. Patients were evaluated for ear discharge and epithelization at 15, 45, and 90 days post-surgery using the Merchant et al grading system for otorrhea.

Results: The study found that 50% of the case group subjects had no or minimal ear discharge on day 15, compared to 20% in the control group. At day 45, 79% of case group subjects attained grade 0 ear discharge, while only 50% of control group subjects did. The study found that 33% of subjects in the case group had epithelisation by day 15, while only 24% attained epithelisation by day 15 in the control group. By day 45, 63% of subjects in the case group had fully formed epithelial tissue, compared to 38% in the control group.

The study found that the use of postauricular soft tissue in CWD mastoidectomy leads to better surgical outcomes, including reduced ear discharge, faster healing, and improved epithelial tissue formation. Specifically, at day 15, 50% of case group subjects had no or minimal ear discharge compared to 20% in the control group, and at day 45, 79% of case group subjects attained grade 0 ear discharge, while only 50% of control group subjects did.

Conclusions

The study concludes that the use of postauricular soft tissue for mastoid cavity obliteration in CWD mastoidectomy leads to better outcomes, including faster healing, less discharge, and improved epithelization.

Key Words

Mastoidectomy, canal wall down mastoidectomy, CWD Mastoidectomy, Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media, CSOM, cholesteatoma, Mastoid Cavity obliteration, Post Auricular soft tissue graft.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SL.NO	TITLE	PAGE NUMBER
1	INTRODUCTION	13
2	AIMS AND OBJECTIVES	21
3	REVIEW OF LITERATURE	22
4	MATERIALS AND METHODS	27
5	RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS	32
6	DISCUSSION	44
7	CONCLUSION	48
8	SUMMARY	49
9	REFERENCES	51
10	ANNEXURES	53
	I. ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE	53
	II. PROFORMA	54
	III. CONSENT FORM	55
	IV. MASTER CHART	58

LIST OF TABLES

SL.NO.	TABLES	PAGE NO.
1.	DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO AGE	32
2	DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO SEX	33
3	DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE IN CASE GROUP	34
4	DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE IN CONTROL GROUP	35
5	DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO SEX: GRADE 0	37
6	DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO SEX: GRADE 1	37
7	DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO SEX: GRADE 2	38
8	DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO SEX: GRADE 3	38
9	DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO AGE: GRADE 0	39
10	DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO AGE: GRADE 1	39
11	DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO AGE: GRADE 2	39
12	DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO AGE: GRADE 3	39
13	DISTRIBUTION OF EPITHELIALISATION IN CASE GROUP	40
14	DISTRIBUTION OF EPITHELIALISATION IN CONTROL GROUP	41
15	DISTRIBUTION OF EPITHELIALISATION WITH AGE	43

LIST OF FIGURES

SL.NO	VARIABLES	PAGE NO.
1	TEMPORAL BONE	15
2	OBLITERATION OF MASTOID CAVITY USING POST AURICULAR SOFT TISSUE	30
3	EPITHELIALISATION ON POD 45	30
4	DRY EAR POD 15	30

LIST OF GRAPHS

SL.NO	VARIABLES	PAGE NO.
1	DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO AGE	32
2	DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO SEX:	33
3	DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO SEX IN BOTH STUDY GROUP	34
4	DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE DAY 15	36
5	DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE DAY 45	36
6	DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE DAY 90	37
7	DISTRIBUTION OF DAY 15 EPITHELIALISATION	41
8	DISTRIBUTION OF DAY 45 EPITHELIALISATION	41
9	DISTRIBUTION OF DAY 90 EPITHELIALISATION	42

INTRODUCTION

Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media (CSOM) is a common ear condition in India and many other parts of the world. The incidence of CSOM is estimated at more than 20 million people worldwide. It is characterized by chronic middle ear and mastoid cavity inflammation, typically leading to persistent ear discharge and hearing loss. recurrent upper respiratory tract infections, poor socioeconomic circumstances, cramped housing, inadequate diet, and cleanliness [1], Inadequate healthcare resources, genetic predisposition, malnourishment, restricted access to healthcare facilities, and structural anomalies such as cleft palate are often associated with the development of CSOM 3. CSOM has two distinct types benign or tubotympanic, which causes a persistent central perforation and mainly affects the inferior anterior portion of the middle ear cleft. People with this kind of CSOM do not typically have serious consequences in spite of this symptom. However, because it affects both the attic and posterosuperior areas of the middle ear, the second classification—known as the malignant or atticotympanic type—is sometimes referred to as the "danger" type and poses a serious risk to the health of those who are affected. [2].

Treatment for CSOM typically involves:

Medical Management: This includes cleaning the ear, prescribing antibiotics to control infection, and using topical medications to manage symptoms. This approach is often suitable for cases where the disease is manageable and has no significant complications.

Surgical Intervention: In cases where medical management is insufficient, surgery may be necessary to repair the eardrum (tympanoplasty) or to perform mastoidectomy, which involves the removal of diseased bone in the mastoid cavity to clear infection and prevent further complications

For the past 150 years, the open mastoidectomy approach has been the cornerstone of the care of cholesteatoma. It has a long and renowned history. Open cavity procedures can be broadly defined as those requiring the removal of the posterior wall of the external auditory canal. These operations go by several

names, including Bondy mastoidectomy, radical mastoidectomy, modified radical mastoidectomy, and canal wall down mastoidectomy -depending on how the middle ear and the disease are managed[3]. The purpose of the open cavity procedure is to exteriorize the mastoid cavity for future monitoring of recurrent cholesteatoma, provide drainage for unresectable temporal bone infection, and occasionally, provide exposure for difficult-to-access areas of the temporal bone[4].

The concept of mastoid obliteration was first introduced in 1911 by Mosher to promote the healing of a mastoidectomy defect. Over the years, numerous reports have detailed various techniques for obliterating the mastoid cavity. Most obliteration techniques consist of local flaps (muscle, periosteum, or fascia) or free grafts (bone, cartilage, hydroxyapatite, and so on). Mosher's original description was that of a superiorly based postauricular soft tissue flap [4].

Mastoid reconstruction and obliteration procedures can be classified into two main categories: a) Free grafts, further subdivided into biologic and non-biologic. b) Local flaps.

Free Grafts: After a CWD mastoidectomy, the mastoid cavity can be filled with cartilage, fat, fascia, allogeneous or autogenous bone chips, and cortical bone pate, among other biologic techniques. Free Grafts: Non-biologic techniques for reconstructing or filling the canal wall after CWD mastoidectomy include the use of bioactive glass ceramics, hydroxyapatite crystals, and ceramic granules of calcium phosphate. Regional A number of different flap types were used, such as the inferiorly based fascial periosteal flap, postauricular myocutaneous flap, pedicled superficial temporalis fascial flap, middle temporal artery flap, Hong Kong flap, temporoparietal fascial flap (TPFF), and temporalis muscle flap.

When treating persistent otitis media, canal wall-down mastoidectomy is the most common reason to consider mastoid obliteration. Even with topical antibiotic medication and regular cavity cleaning, a canal wall down the mastoid cavity can cause persistent otorrhea that can be challenging to control. A mastoid cavity can also cause other issues like frequent cleaning, trouble using a hearing aid, water intolerance

because of an increased risk of infection, and a tendency to become dizzy when exposed to caloric stimuli like water or warm/cold air. It is recommended to obliterate the mastoid cavity in order to decrease the cavity's size. The best time to perform it is during a canal wall-down mastoidectomy as a primary surgery. Our ENT Department performs standard surgery such as mastoid cavity obliteration and canal wall down mastoidectomy. Thus, in order to manage the riskier varieties of CSOM, we need to investigate the outcomes and advantages of this process.[5].

TEMPORAL BONE ANATOMY

IMAGE REPRESENTATION 1- TEMPORAL BONE

The temporal bone is a complex structure located on the sides and base of the skull, encompassing the region around the ear. It plays a crucial role in housing the structures of the ear and protecting the delicate organs involved in hearing and balance. Here's a detailed overview of its anatomy[6]

Main Parts of the Temporal Bone

1. **Squamous Part:**
 - The largest part, it forms the front and upper portion of the temporal bone.
 - Contains the zygomatic process, which connects to the zygomatic bone (cheekbone).
2. **Tympanic Part:**
 - Surrounds the external acoustic meatus (ear canal).
 - Forms the front and lower walls of the ear canal.
3. **Mastoid Part:**
 - Located behind the ear, this part contains the mastoid process, a bony projection.
 - The mastoid process is filled with air cells that communicate with the middle ear cavity.
4. **Petrous Part:**
 - The most complex part, it is located at the base of the skull.
 - Houses the inner ear structures, including the cochlea (responsible for hearing) and the vestibular system (responsible for balance).
 - Contains the internal acoustic meatus, through which the facial and vestibulocochlear nerves pass.[6,7]

Key Structures

1. **External Acoustic Meatus (Ear Canal):**
 - Leads sound waves from the external ear to the tympanic membrane (eardrum).
2. **Middle Ear:**
 - Contains the ossicles (malleus, incus, stapes), which transmit sound vibrations from the tympanic membrane to the inner ear.
 - The Eustachian tube connects the middle ear to the nasopharynx, helping to equalize pressure.
3. **Inner Ear:**
 - Comprises the cochlea, vestibule, and semicircular canals.
 - The cochlea converts sound vibrations into neural signals.
 - The vestibule and semicircular canals are involved in balance and spatial orientation.
4. **Mastoid Air Cells:**
 - A network of air-filled spaces within the mastoid process.
 - Communicate with the middle ear and play a role in protecting the ear structures from infections.
5. **Stylomastoid Foramen:**
 - Located between the styloid and mastoid processes.
 - The facial nerve exits the skull through this foramen.[6,7]

Clinical Significance

- **Mastoiditis:** Infection of the mastoid air cells, often resulting from untreated middle ear infections.
- **Temporal Bone Fractures:** Can affect hearing and balance due to damage to the structures within the bone.
- **Otitis Media:** Inflammation of the middle ear, which can spread to the mastoid part.

The temporal bone's intricate anatomy underscores its importance in the auditory and vestibular systems, providing both structural support and protection for the critical organs involved in these senses.[7]

Mastoidectomy

A mastoidectomy is a surgical procedure performed to remove infected mastoid air cells located within the mastoid process, a part of the temporal bone behind the ear. This procedure is commonly conducted to treat chronic ear infections that have not responded to other treatments, or to remove cholesteatoma, a growth of skin cells that can damage ear structures. [8]

Types of Mastoidectomy[8]

1. **Simple (or Closed) Mastoidectomy:**
 - Involves the removal of the mastoid air cells without disturbing the ear canal or the eardrum.
 - Typically used to treat infections confined to the mastoid area.
2. **Radical Mastoidectomy:**
 - More extensive, involving the removal of the mastoid air cells, the eardrum, and the ossicles (bones of the middle ear).
 - Often used for extensive disease, such as large cholesteatomas.
 - Results in significant hearing loss because the middle ear structures are removed.
3. **Modified Radical Mastoidectomy:**
 - Similar to a radical mastoidectomy but preserves the ear canal and often some of the ossicles.
 - Balances disease removal with the preservation of some hearing.
4. **Canal Wall Down Mastoidectomy:**
 - The posterior and superior canal walls are removed to create a common cavity with the mastoid air cells.
 - Often used in cases of extensive disease.
5. **Canal Wall Up Mastoidectomy:**
 - The canal walls are left intact.
 - Maintains a more natural ear anatomy but may require further surgery if the disease recurs.

Canal Wall Down Mastoidectomy (CWD)

A Canal Wall Down Mastoidectomy is a surgical procedure designed to treat chronic ear infections and cholesteatomas by removing part of the bony ear canal wall to create a single large cavity. This procedure provides better access to the mastoid and middle ear spaces, reducing the risk of residual disease and recurrent infections.[9]

Indications

- **Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media (CSOM):** Persistent and severe ear infections that do not respond to medical treatment.

- **Cholesteatoma:** An abnormal skin growth in the middle ear that can cause chronic infections and damage to ear structures.
- **Complications of Otitis Media:** Including brain abscess, meningitis, or facial nerve paralysis.
- **Tumors:** Benign or malignant growths in the ear or mastoid area.[10]

Complications of Canal Wall Down Mastoidectomy

While Canal Wall Down Mastoidectomy (CWD) is effective in managing chronic ear infections and cholesteatomas, it carries potential risks and complications. Understanding these can help in preoperative counseling and postoperative care.[9,10]

1. Hearing Loss

- **Conductive Hearing Loss:** Due to removal or damage to ossicles (middle ear bones).
- **Sensorineural Hearing Loss:** Can occur if inner ear structures are affected during surgery.

2. Facial Nerve Injury

- The facial nerve runs close to the surgical site, and inadvertent damage can cause facial paralysis or weakness.

3. Dizziness and Vertigo

- Manipulation of the inner ear structures can lead to postoperative dizziness or vertigo, which can be temporary or, rarely, permanent.

4. Chronic Ear Discharge (Otorrhea)

- Despite the surgery, some patients may experience persistent or recurrent ear discharge due to incomplete removal of diseased tissue or ongoing infections.

5. Infection

- The creation of a large cavity can predispose to infections if not properly managed and cleaned.

6. Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF) Leak

- Rarely, if the dura mater is breached during surgery, it can lead to a CSF leak, which requires immediate attention.

7. Cholesteatoma Recurrence

- Even with thorough removal, there is a risk of residual cholesteatoma or regrowth, necessitating regular follow-up and possibly additional surgery.

8. Taste Disturbance

- The chorda tympani nerve, which affects taste, can be damaged during surgery, leading to altered taste sensation.

9. Tinnitus

- Patients may experience or have an increase in tinnitus (ringing in the ear) postoperatively.

10. Granulation Tissue Formation

- Excessive granulation tissue can form in the surgical cavity, leading to discomfort and the need for further interventions.

11. Hearing Aid Considerations

- Patients with CWD mastoidectomy often require a modified approach to fitting hearing aids due to the altered ear anatomy.

12. Aesthetic Concerns

- The removal of part of the ear canal wall can sometimes lead to cosmetic issues, such as a visible cavity or asymmetry.

13. Need for Lifelong Maintenance

- The open cavity created by the surgery requires regular cleaning and monitoring to prevent infection and ensure proper drainage.

Mastoid Cavity Obliteration

Mastoid cavity obliteration is a surgical technique used to manage chronic ear infections and cholesteatoma. This procedure involves filling the mastoid cavity, created during a mastoidectomy, with various materials to promote healing, prevent infection, and improve the overall outcome of the surgery.[11]

Purpose of Mastoid Cavity Obliteration

1. **Preventing Chronic Infection:** By filling the cavity, the risk of chronic infection and persistent ear discharge (otorrhea) is reduced.
2. **Improving Healing:** Obliteration provides a scaffold for tissue growth, enhancing the healing process.
3. **Reducing Cavity Size:** This makes postoperative care easier and reduces the risk of debris accumulation and recurrent infections.
4. **Improving Aesthetic and Functional Outcomes:** A smaller, obliterated cavity can lead to better cosmetic results and improve the fit of hearing aids if needed.[10,11]

Benefits of Mastoid Cavity Obliteration

Mastoid cavity obliteration is a surgical procedure that offers several benefits, particularly for patients who undergo mastoidectomy for chronic ear infections or cholesteatoma. Here are some key benefits of mastoid cavity obliteration:

1. **Reduced Infection Rates:**
 - By filling the mastoid cavity, obliteration decreases the risk of chronic infections. The filled cavity is less prone to harbor bacteria and other pathogens that can lead to recurrent ear infections.
2. **Enhanced Healing:**
 - The obliteration process provides a scaffold for tissue regeneration. This leads to quicker and more effective healing, as the materials used for obliteration, such as muscle flaps or bone pâté, are well-vascularized and support new tissue growth.
3. **Improved Patient Comfort:**
 - A smaller and more stable obliterated cavity results in less postoperative maintenance. Patients experience fewer issues with ear discharge and debris accumulation, making daily care easier and more comfortable.
4. **Better Cosmetic and Functional Outcomes:**
 - Obliteration helps in reducing the size of the mastoid cavity, which can improve the cosmetic appearance of the ear. Additionally, it can lead to better functional outcomes, especially for patients who use hearing aids.
5. **Decreased Need for Revision Surgery:**
 - The stability and durability of the obliterated cavity reduce the likelihood of needing additional surgical interventions. This is particularly beneficial for patients with chronic conditions that would otherwise require frequent medical attention.
6. **Prevention of Chronic Discharge:**
 - By promoting efficient drainage and preventing the accumulation of secretions, mastoid cavity obliteration minimizes the risk of persistent ear discharge (otorrhea).
7. **Long-Term Stability:**
 - Using the patient's own tissues (autologous materials) for obliteration ensures better integration and less risk of rejection or complications associated with foreign materials. This leads to long-term stability and fewer recurrences of disease.
8. **Less Frequent Medical Interventions:**
 - Patients with an obliterated mastoid cavity often require less frequent medical interventions for infections or complications, which improves their overall quality of life and reduces healthcare costs.[9–11]

- **AIMS**

To assess the surgical outcome of patients undergoing obliteration of mastoid cavity with postauricular soft tissue in canal wall down mastoidectomy for Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media with Cholesteatoma.

- **OBJECTIVES**

1. To Look for ear discharge from mastoid cavity on Post of Day 15, 45, 90
2. To Look for Epithelisation on mastoid cavity on post of Day 15, 45, 90

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The study "Surgical Outcome of Mastoid Cavity Obliteration with Postauricular Soft Tissue in Canal Wall Down Mastoidectomy" by Dr. Navneet Mathur[3] and colleagues investigated the effectiveness of using postauricular soft tissue for mastoid cavity obliteration in canal wall down mastoidectomy (CWDM) procedures. It involved a cohort of patients undergoing CWDM for chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) with cholesteatoma. Comprehensive assessment of patients with chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) and cholesteatoma. Detailed history and clinical examination, including otoscopic and audiometric evaluations. Imaging studies such as CT scans to assess the extent of disease was done. The researchers used postauricular soft tissue, including periosteum and musculoperiosteal flaps, to obliterate the mastoid cavity. For a duration of one week, each patient received an antibiotic, analgesic, and antihistaminic drug. Two weeks following surgery the ear pack was removed and they were scheduled for follow-up appointments one week and one month. The study found that obliteration of the mastoid cavity using postauricular soft tissue significantly reduced the incidence of persistent ear discharge, a common complication in CWDM. The majority of patients achieved a dry, stable cavity with good healing outcomes. Audiometric evaluations indicated that hearing outcomes were maintained or improved in most cases, with minimal postoperative complications. [12]

The study's conclusions included the following ones.

- 1) There was a significant decrease in the frequency of pain, discharge, giddiness, and wax formation in obliterated cavities in contrast to those that are still open.
- 2) In comparison to ears where the cavity was left open, ears where the cavity was completely obliterated had superior cavity healing as shown by epithelization.
- 3) Patients who had their mastoid cavities obliterated needed less cavity care, which reduced the need for frequent OPD visits, shorter courses of treatment.

- 4) The mastoid oblitative group saw a greater increase in hearing than the non-oblitative group.
- 5) The oblitative group's cavity dried more quickly than the non-oblitative group's.
- 6) The oblitative group experienced a lower rate of complications than the non-oblitative group.⁴

Shah et al. (2020)[12] Study on Mastoid Obliteration with Postauricular Composite Bone and Periosteum Flap. The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of using postauricular composite bone along with a periosteum flap for mastoid cavity obliteration in patients undergoing canal wall down (CWD) mastoidectomy for chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) with cholesteatoma. patients diagnosed with CSOM requiring CWD mastoidectomy was included in the study. Comprehensive preoperative assessments including clinical examination, audiometry, and imaging was done. The postauricular composite bone, including the cortical bone and periosteum, was harvested. The harvested composite bone and periosteum flap were used to obliterate the mastoid cavity. The composite bone was positioned in the cavity, followed by the periosteum flap to cover and secure the obliterated area. The use of postauricular composite bone and periosteum flap significantly improved the healing time. There was a notable reduction in postoperative complications, including persistent discharge and infection. Audiometric evaluations indicated stable or improved hearing outcomes in most patients. High levels of patient satisfaction were reported due to improved functional and cosmetic results. The study concluded that using postauricular composite bone with a periosteum flap for mastoid cavity obliteration in CWD mastoidectomy is an effective technique. It promotes rapid healing, reduces postoperative complications, and maintains or improves hearing function, resulting in high patient satisfaction.[12]

The study "Periosteal-temporofascial Flap for Cavity Obliteration—First Indian Study" conducted by V. Wadhwa, T.S. Anand, S. Kumar, G. Kasthuria, and I. Rana [13] is a pioneering research project in India focused on evaluating the effectiveness of using a periosteal-

temporofascial flap for mastoid cavity obliteration in canal wall down (CWD) mastoidectomy procedures. The main aim of the study was to assess the success and complications associated with using a periosteal-temporofascial flap for obliterating the mastoid cavity to reduce postoperative complications such as infection and persistent otorrhea. The study included both retrospective and prospective analyses of patients undergoing CWD mastoidectomy for chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM). The study involved a cohort of patients diagnosed with CSOM who required CWD mastoidectomy. The periosteal-temporofascial flap was harvested from the temporalis muscle and surrounding periosteum. The harvested flap was used to obliterate the mastoid cavity, ensuring a well-vascularized coverage of the entire cavity to promote healing. The flap was carefully placed and secured in the mastoid cavity. Regular follow-ups were conducted to monitor healing, infection rates, and the overall condition of the mastoid cavity. Audiometric evaluations were performed to assess hearing outcomes. The study reported a significant reduction in the healing time of the mastoid cavity. There was a marked decrease in postoperative infections and chronic discharge. The size of the mastoid cavity was effectively reduced, making maintenance easier and improving patient comfort. High levels of patient satisfaction were observed due to improved functional and cosmetic outcomes. The study concluded that using a periosteal-temporofascial flap for mastoid cavity obliteration in CWD mastoidectomy is an effective technique. It promotes rapid healing, reduces the risk of postoperative complications, and enhances patient satisfaction, providing a significant advancement in otologic surgery in India.[13]

Long-Term Results of Canal Wall Down Mastoidectomy with Obliteration by Sergi et al. (2010). The primary aim of the study was to assess the long-term outcomes of canal wall down (CWD) mastoidectomy with various techniques for mastoid cavity obliteration. The study focused on evaluating the effectiveness, complications, and patient satisfaction associated with different obliteration materials and methods. The study included a cohort of patients who underwent CWD

mastoidectomy with obliteration. Patients were followed up for an extended period to monitor long-term outcomes. Different materials were used for obliteration, including Muscle flaps, Bone pate, Alloplastic materials (e.g., hydroxyapatite cement). Each technique aimed to fill the mastoid cavity, promote healing, and prevent chronic infection and drainage. Regular follow-ups were conducted to assess the surgical site, healing process, and any complications. Audiometric evaluations were performed to monitor hearing outcomes. The study reported positive outcomes in terms of cavity healing and reduced complications. Patients with obliterated cavities had fewer issues with chronic drainage and infections compared to those without obliteration. The incidence of complications varied depending on the obliteration material used, with muscle flaps and bone pate showing favorable results. Hearing results were generally stable or improved postoperatively. The study emphasized the importance of meticulous surgical technique to preserve or enhance hearing function. High levels of patient satisfaction were reported due to improved ear health, reduced need for frequent cleanings, and better cosmetic outcomes. Patients with successful cavity obliteration experienced a significant improvement in their quality of life. The study concluded that canal wall down mastoidectomy with cavity obliteration is an effective surgical approach for managing chronic suppurative otitis media. The choice of obliteration material is critical to the success of the procedure, with muscle flaps and bone pate being particularly effective. Long-term follow-up demonstrated that obliteration significantly reduces postoperative complications and improves patient outcomes [13,14]

Obliteration of the Mastoid Cavity with Hydroxyapatite Cement by Hunter et al. (2006). The primary aim of the study was to evaluate the efficacy and safety of using hydroxyapatite cement for the obliteration of the mastoid cavity following canal wall down (CWD) mastoidectomy. The study focused on the outcomes related to infection rates, cavity healing, and patient satisfaction. Patients undergoing CWD mastoidectomy for chronic suppurative otitis media were selected for the study. Inclusion criteria included patients with recurrent infections, cholesteatoma, or chronic ear

drainage requiring surgical intervention. Hydroxyapatite cement was used to fill the mastoid cavity. The cement was carefully molded and placed into the cavity to ensure complete obliteration. The surgical site was closed, and patients were monitored postoperatively. Regular follow-ups were conducted to monitor for signs of infection, proper healing of the cavity, and overall patient outcomes. Audiometric evaluations were performed to assess any changes in hearing. The study reported high success rates with the use of hydroxyapatite cement for cavity obliteration. There was a significant reduction in postoperative infections and chronic drainage. The healing process was found to be efficient, with most patients showing complete epithelialization of the cavity. Audiometric evaluations indicated stable or improved hearing outcomes post-surgery. The obliteration process did not adversely affect the auditory function of the patients. High levels of patient satisfaction were reported, primarily due to the reduction in chronic infections and the improved condition of the ear. Patients also appreciated the decreased need for frequent medical interventions and cleanings. The study concluded that hydroxyapatite cement is an effective material for the obliteration of the mastoid cavity following CWD mastoidectomy. Its use significantly reduces postoperative complications, promotes efficient healing, and results in high patient satisfaction. The findings support the use of hydroxyapatite cement as a reliable option for mastoid cavity obliteration.[15]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SOURCE OF DATA:

Study Design: Hospital based Prospective Study.

Study Duration: From 30 August 2022 to 30 February 2024

Sample Size: 48 (24 Case Group + 24 Control Group)

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- 1) All CSOM cases with cholesteatoma.
- 2) CSOM with extensive granulations.
- 3) Recurrent cases of cholesteatoma.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- 1) Unwilling patients
- 2) Known CSOM cases with intracranial complications
- 3) Tubercular otitis media

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA

- All patients underwent detailed medical history and clinical examination. Each patient have to undergo otoscopic examination, PTA, bilateral mastoid x-ray and HRCT temporal bone (if needed). The primary measure is to create of a dry, infection free, low maintenance mastoid cavity as assessed by a grading system developed by Merchant et al., [16] The semi quantitative scale takes into consideration both patient symptomatology and clinical sign such as otorrhea and the presence of infection. The scale ranges from grade 0, representing a complete dry, healed ear, through to grade 3.[16]

Merchant Et al. Grading for Ear Discharge[16]

- **Grade 0:** No episode of otorrhea, and no pus or granulation tissue on otoscopy.
- **Grade 1:** One episode of otorrhea of 2 weeks or demonstration of localized granulation tissue/ pus that was promptly cured with antibiotic drops, curettage or vinegar drops.
- **Grade 2:** More than one episode of otorrhea in a 3-month period, or an episode of otorrhea lasting >2 weeks or demonstration of localized granulation tissue/ pus that was promptly cured with antibiotic drops, curettage or vinegar drops.
- **Grade 3:** Constant purulent otorrhea on a daily basis, or examination showing extensive granulation tissue, or needed for a revision procedure to control infection. Grades 0,1and 2 are considered adequate control of infection, whereas grade 3 indicate failure of control of infection. [16]

SURGICAL PROCEDURE

- Following GA induction, the ear was cleaned by cleaning the auricle and post-auricular area and inserting spirit and povidone iodine solution into the ear canal.
- Lignocaine with 1:100000 epinephrine was injected into the post auricular region and the ear canal for hemostasis. .
- A post auricular william wildes incision was made in the post auricular skin crease and temporalis fascia graft harvested.T shaped incision given mucoperichondrial and mucoperiosteal flap elevated.
- Post auricular soft tissue graft harvested.
- A cutting burr was used to perform simple mastoidectomy. At this point, the granulations and cholesteatoma that were occupying the central mastoid tracts were removed.
- The facial ridge can be reduced till a thin layer of bone is removed across the vertical segment of the facial nerve after the posterior canal wall was securely removed.
- anterior and posterior buttress was removed.
- The ossicular chain was examined, and those that were unhealthy were removed.
- Total clearance of cholesteatoma and granulation from mastoid cavity, attic and middle ear was done along with saucerization of mastoid cavity.
- followed by underlay tympanoplasty, anterior tugging and ossiculoplasty.
- Free skin grafting over the fascia and bone was done and abgel foam kept insitu.
- Mastoid cavity was now obliterated by extending the post auricular soft tissue. Following which meatoplasty done and Haemostasis achieved and suturing done with vicryl 3.0 and ethylon 3.0[17]

IMAGE REPRESENTATION 2- OBLITERATION OF MASTOID CAVITY USING POST-AURICULAR SOFT TISSUE

IMAGE REPRESENTATION 2A- OBLITERATION OF MASTOID CAVITY USING POST-AURICULAR SOFT TISSUE

IMAGE REPRESENTATION 3 - EPITHELISATION ON POD 45

IMAGE REPRESENTATION 4- DRY EAR POD 15

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Descriptive summary is done for all characters .Statistics of N, mean, median, IQR and standard deviation (SD) are used. For categorical data, the number and percentage will be used in the data summaries and is analyzed by Chi square test or Fishers exact test for association, comparison of means using, sensitivity, specificity and diagrammatic presentation.

By using the formula:

$$n = \frac{z^2 p(1-p)}{d^2}$$

where

Z= z statistic at 5% level of significance

d is margin of error

p is maximum anticipated prevalence rate

If the p- value was less than (<0.05) , then the results were considered to be statistically significant.

RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO AGE:

Age Category	Cases	Controls
< 18 years	8	4
18-35 years	6	9
36-50 years	5	7
>50 years	5	4
Total	24	24

Out of 48 patients enrolled maximum patients were in between the age group 18-35 years

GRAPH 1: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO AGE

In our study we found that the samples were distributed among 4 age groups, with mean age of 30.4 in case group and 34.7 in control group.

TABLE 2: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO SEX:

Gender	Cases	Controls	Total
Female	8 (33.3%)	15(62.5%)	23 (47.9%)
Male	16 (66.7%)	9 (37.5%)	25 (52.1%)
Total	24	24	100.0%

Out of 48 patients enrolled in the study 23 (47.9%) were females, 25 (52.1%) were males.

GRAPH 2: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO SEX:

GRAPH 3: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO SEX IN BOTH STUDY GROUPS

In our study, 52% of the population is comprised of males, with 16 subjects in the case group and 9 in the control group. At the same time, females comprised 48%, with 8 in the case group and 15 in the control group. In this study, we can see more than 60% of study subjects in the case group are male and the control group is female.

TABLE 3: DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE IN CASES GROUP

CASES	Day 15	Day 45	Day 90
Grade 0	12	19	21
Grade 1	6	3	2
Grade 2	4	1	0
Grade 3	2	1	1
Total	24	24	24

In this study, we examined the ear discharge post 15 days of surgery under oto-endoscopy, which revealed that in the case group of 24 subjects, 50% of the study population had grade 0 ear discharge, where only 6 (25%) subjects tend to have grade 1, 4 subjects (16%) had grade 2 and 2 subjects (8%) had grade 3 ear

discharge.

Later on, examining the ear discharge on day 45, we observed that 19 case subjects (79%) having grade 0 discharge, and out of 6 subjects having previous grade 1 discharge, were reduced to 3, and we see a 75% decline in several subjects in grade 2 category over 30 days. Regarding grade 3, we see a 50% decline in several subjects. On observing the ear discharge status after 90 days, the study revealed that 87% of subjects had no discharge over 90 days, with a major decline in the number of subjects in grade 2 and grade 3.

TABLE 4: DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE IN CONTROL GROUP

Controls	Day 15	Day 45	Day 90
Grade 0	5	12	16
Grade 1	4	3	4
Grade 2	5	5	2
Grade 3	10	4	2
Total	24	24	24

On observing the control group of our study, after 15 days of examination for ear discharge, it was revealed that 5 (20%) of the sample had grade 0 ear discharge, and around 20% of the sample were in grade 1 and grade 2 categories.

When we see the study data, 41% of the study population has grade 3 ear discharge post 15 days of surgery in the control group. The study revealed that on 45 days and 90 days of ear discharge examination, we found 50% and 66% of the case group with grade 0 ear discharge.

In this study, we observe that the day 15 ear examination revealed the majority of the sample had grade 3 ear discharge, with the majority of the sample on both day 45 and day 90 having grade 0 ear discharge.

GRAPH 4: DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE ON DAY 15:

GRAPH 5: DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE ON DAY 45:

GRAPH 6: DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE ON DAY 90:

TABLE 5: DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO SEX- GRADE 0

GRADE 0	MALES		FEMALES	
	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES
DAY 15	1	7	4	5
DAY 45	3	12	9	7
DAY 90	4	14	12	7

TABLE 6: DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO SEX-GRADE 1

GRADE 1	MALES		FEMALES	
	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES
DAY 15	1	5	3	1
DAY 45	1	3	2	0
DAY 90	2	1	2	1

TABLE 7: DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO SEX GRADE 2

GRADE 2	MALES		FEMALES	
	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES
DAY 15	1	3	4	1
DAY 45	3	0	2	1
DAY 90	1	0	1	0

TABLE 8: DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO SEX GRADE 3

GRADE 3	MALES		FEMALES	
	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES
DAY 15	6	1	4	1
DAY 45	2	1	2	0
DAY 90	2	1	0	0

In this study, we found that most of the 66% of control samples had grade 3 discharge on day 15, while 44% of case group males had grade 0 ear discharge. 31% of case group males had grade 1 ear discharge, 18% with grade 2 ear discharge, and 1 out of 16 males in the case group had grade 3 ear discharge on post of day 15. While analysing the result among females of both the control and case groups, data was scattered among the control group, with 26% of the sample having grade 0, 1, and 3 ear discharge, while 20% of the sample had grade 2 ear discharge.

On analysing the females in case group, we found out that 63% of samples had grade 0 ear discharge with an equal amount of prevalence in all other three categories. On analysing the data for ear discharge on days 45 and 90, we found that almost 33% of samples had grade 0 ear discharge. At the same time, 75% and 87% of male samples from case group had grade 0 ear discharge on days 45 and 90, respectively.

Looking at the female samples, we found 60 % and 80% of females in the control group had grade 0 ear discharge on post-days 45 and 90. At the same time, 77% of female samples in case group have attained grade 0 ear discharge by day 45 and 90.

TABLE 9: DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO AGE : GRADE 0

GRADE 0	<18		18-35		36-50		>50	
	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROL	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES
DAY 15	0	6	4	3	1	1	1	2
DAY 45	1	8	8	5	2	4	0	2
DAY 90	2	8	9	5	4	5	1	3

TABLE 10: DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO AGE : GRADE 1

GRADE 1	<18		18-35		36-50		>50	
	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROL	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES
DAY 15	2	2	2	2	0	2	0	0
DAY 45	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
DAY 90	1	0	0	1	2	0	1	1

TABLE 11: DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO AGE : GRADE 2

GRADE 2	<18		18-35		36-50		>50	
	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROL	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES
DAY 15	0	0	2	1	2	2	1	1
DAY 45	1	0	0	0	4	0	0	1
DAY 90	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0

TABLE 12: DISTRIBUTION OF EAR DISCHARGE TO AGE : GRADE 3

GRADE 3	<18		18-35		36-50		>50	
	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROL	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES
DAY 15	2	0	1	0	4	0	3	2
DAY 45	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	1
DAY 90	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1

In the study, we found that 75% of samples from the case group in the age group of less than 18 years had grade 0 ear discharge, while none among the control group had grade 0 ear discharge.

While 100% of samples from the case group in the age group of 18 years have attained grade 0 ear discharge by days 45 and 90, at the same time, everyone in control group attained grade 0 ear discharge by day 90.

In the 18-35 years age group, we see 50% of the case group attained grade 0 ear discharge by day 15, and 83% of the case group attained grade 0 by day 45 and 90 post surgery. At the same time, 44% of samples from the control group attained grade 0 ear discharge by day 15, 88% by day 45 and 100% by day 90.

In the 36-50 years age group, we found that 57% of control group subjects were having grade 3 ear discharge on day 15. Later on the day, 90 57% of control group subjects attained grade 0 ear discharge. At the same time, one among the 5 subjects have attained grade 0 ear discharge on day 15 post surgery. While 80% of case group have attained grade 0 discharge by day 45, and 100% have attained grade 0 by 90 days post surgery.

On analysing the age group of more than 50 years, we found that 60% of samples in the control group had grade 3 ear discharge, while only 20% had grade 0 discharge by day 15. While in the case group, we observed that 40% of samples had grade 0 and grade 3 ear discharge on day 15, and 60% of samples attained grade 0 discharge by day 90 post-surgery.

TABLE 13: DISTRIBUTION OF EPITHELISATION IN CASE GROUP

CASES	Day 15	Day 45	Day 90
YES	8	15	21
NO	16	9	3

In this study, we found that eight among 24 (33%) subjects in the case group attained epithelisation by day 15 post-surgery, while 63% of subjects achieved epithelisation by day 45 and 88% attained epithelisation by day 90 post-surgery.

TABLE 14: DISTRIBUTION OF EPITHELISATION IN CONTROL GROUP

CONTROLS	Day 15	Day 45	Day 90
YES	1	9	13
NO	23	15	11

Among the control group of study, we observe that only one among the 24 (4%) subjects attained epithelisation on day 15 post-surgery, 38% of control group subjects attained epithelisation by day 45, and only 54% of subjects attained epithelisation by day 90.

GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION 7: DISTRIBUTION OF EPITHELISATION ON DAY 15

GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION 8: DISTRIBUTION OF EPITHELISATION ON DAY 45

GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION 9: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO EPITHELISATION DAY 90

TABLE 13: DISTRIBUTION OF EPITHELISATION WITH AGE

EPI FORMED	<18		18-35		36-50		>50	
	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES	CONTROL	CASES	CONTROLS	CASES
DAY 15	0	4	1	3	0	0	0	1
DAY 45	1	6	8	5	0	3	0	1
DAY 90	2	8	8	5	1	5	1	3

While analyzing the epithelisation among various age groups, we found that among subjects under 18, initially, 50 % of subjects in the case group attained epithelisation by day 15. In contrast, no subjects among the control group attained epithelisation by day 15. On day 45, we observed that six among eight subjects in the case group had attained epithelisation by day 45 and all 8 case group subjects (100%) in the age group less than 18 had attained epithelisation, compared to a control group where all subjects attained epithelisation by day 90.

In the age group 18-35 years age group, we observed that one among the eight subjects in the control group has attained epithelisation by day 15 post-surgery, and all subjects (100%) attained

epithelisation by day 45. On comparing with the case group of the same age group, 60% of subjects have attained epithelisation by day 15, and 100% have attained epithelisation by day 45 post-surgery.

On analyzing the age group 36-50 years old, we observed that only one among the four subjects had attained epithelisation by day 90 post-surgery; on comparing it with the case group, none among the five have attained epithelisation by day 15, while 60 % have achieved epithelisation by day 45 and 100% subjects have attained epithelisation by day 90.

Later on, analyzing the age group above 50 years, we found that 100% of subjects from the control group attained epithelisation on day 90. While 20% of subjects in the case group have attained epithelisation by day 15, and 60% of samples have attained epithelisation by day 90 post-surgery.

DISCUSSION

Our study was done on 48 subjects with CSOM, who were divided equally into case and control groups, with mean ages of 30.4 and 34.7, respectively. The study consisted of 23 females (48%) and 25 males (52%); the study was done over 90 days post-surgery, where the patient was evaluated for discharge and epithelisation post-surgery. Each patient was assessed on days 15, 45 and 90 post-surgery, where ear discharge was assessed using the Merchant et al. grading system for Otitorhea.

In our study, we assessed both the case and control groups for ear discharge, revealing that 50% of the case subjects had no or minimal ear discharge on day 15, compared to a control group, where only 20% had grade 0 ear discharge. Later on, assessing the ear discharge on day 45, 50% of the control group subjattained grade 0 ear discharge, while the other had minimal to continuous ear discharge, whereas the case group attained 79% grade 0 ear discharge by day 45. A study by Dr. Navneet Mathur in 2021[3] evaluated the outcomes of using postauricular soft tissue for mastoid cavity obliteration in patients undergoing Canal Wall Down (CWD) mastoidectomy, where he observed that this surgical method has better outcomes than the conventional method, where closure of canal with post auricle soft tissue helps in faster healing and less discharge compared with the traditional method. The study highlights the outcome for the following reasons: firstly, the postauricular soft tissue provides an effective barrier, sealing the mastoid cavity and preventing the entry of infectious agents. Secondly, the obliteration technique enhances the drainage of residual secretions, reducing the likelihood of discharge accumulation. Thirdly, the well-vascularized postauricular soft tissue promotes quicker and more effective healing, reducing inflammation and discharge,. Finally, filling the cavity reduces the soft tissue's size, making it easier to manage and less prone to chronic discharge issues.

In our study, we analyzed the results for the relationship between gender and the outcome of surgery, where we first analyzed the ear discharge in both study groups. The study revealed that 66% of male subjects in the control group had grade 3 ear discharge, compared to 6% in the case group. When

looking at the female gender, we observe that 26 % of females in the control group had all four grades of ear discharge, while 63% of females in the case group had attained grade 0 ear discharge by day 15. This data provides evidence that gender does play a substantial role in the healing process, where the use of a postauricular flap has an evident role in better and faster healing compared to traditional CWD surgery techniques. A study done by Asfa Naimi Mohamad Yusof et al. in 2023[18] assessed the outcomes of Canal wall-down mastoidectomy in cholesteatoma. It indicated that there was an equal distribution of gender among patients undergoing the surgery, though historically, males have been reported to have a higher incidence of cholesteatoma compared to females, which is consistent with our study. The reason that may be possible for better wound healing in females may be due to the effect of hormonal differences they have, as estrogen can promote wound healing by enhancing collagen production, angiogenesis, and inflammatory responses. This hormone is more prevalent in females and plays a significant role in tissue repair and regeneration, and Females often have a more robust immune response than males. This can lead to more efficient clearance of infections and better overall healing. Studies suggest that sex hormones influence the immune system, with estrogen enhancing and androgens (like testosterone) sometimes suppressing immune responses. [19,20]

In our study, we also evaluated any relationship between age and the outcome of both surgeries; the study revealed that the younger age group had better healing, where 100% of samples in the case group attained grade 0 ear discharge by day 45. Still, the control group took 90 days for the same. When observing the older age group, we see that healing was slow and took longer. When comparing both groups, we observe that the case group showed better and faster healing than the control group. The study provides robust data on the effectiveness of using a post-uricular flap for canal walls down mastoidectomy. Various studies, including a survey by Navneet Mathur,[3] have reported the role of age in surgical healing; generally, younger patients tend to have better healing outcomes due to higher cellular regeneration capabilities, more robust immune responses, and better overall health status. Healing can be slower in older patients due to reduced cellular regeneration, weaker immune responses, and the presence of comorbidities

that can complicate recovery. The bone quality in younger individuals is typically better, facilitating easier surgical manipulation and better outcomes. Osteopenia or osteoporosis can be more common in older patients, potentially complicating the surgery and affecting the stability and integration of grafts used in mastoid cavity obliteration. Chronic conditions such as diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and hypertension, which are more prevalent in older populations, can negatively impact surgical outcomes and prolong healing times [19,21]

In this study, we evaluated both groups for the formation of epithelial tissue on days 15, 45 and 90 post-surgery; the study found that 33% of subjects in the case group had epithelisation by day 15 while only 24% attained epithelisation by day 15. Comparing both groups on days 45 and 90, we see that 63% and 88% of subjects have fully formed epithelial tissue over the surgical site in the case group, compared to 38% and 54% in the control group. The study highlights the benefits of using a postauricular flap in faster and better healing compared to the normal formation of epithelial tissue in surgery where no flaps are used. Study by Navneet Arthur et al in assessing the surgical outcome of using post auricular flap, have also found out that use of post auricular flap leads to better outcome in canal wall down mastoidectomy. He explains that post-auricular flaps have a significant role in the reduction of the incidence of chronic infections. The postauricular soft tissue helped seal the mastoid cavity, creating a more stable environment that is less prone to infections. Patients experienced fewer episodes of otorrhea (ear discharge) and required less frequent medical intervention for infections. The study also explained that the postauricular flap, rich in blood vessels, promoted better healing by ensuring a robust blood supply to the obliterated area. This vascularization was crucial in reducing healing times and improving overall surgical outcomes. Using the patient's tissue minimized the risk of rejection and graft complications. The compatibility of the autologous tissue led to better integration and fewer instances of adverse reactions or infections. The use of postauricular soft tissue provided durable and stable results over the long term. Patients experienced fewer recurrences of disease and less need for revision surgeries. [22–24]

Future of mastoid cavity obliteration with postauricular soft tissue in canal wall down (CWD) mastoidectomy is likely to see several advancements and refinements aimed at improving patient outcomes, surgical efficiency, and overall healthcare effectiveness, especially with 1) **Minimally Invasive Approaches**: Advances in endoscopic and minimally invasive surgical techniques could reduce surgical trauma, improve precision, and enhance recovery times. These techniques may allow for better visualization and access during surgery, leading to more effective obliteration and fewer complications. 2) **Advanced Grafting Materials**: The development of new biomaterials that mimic the properties of natural tissue more closely could enhance the success of mastoid cavity obliteration. These materials might include bioactive scaffolds that promote tissue integration and healing.[18,25]

CONCLUSION

The study on the surgical outcome of mastoid cavity obliteration using postauricular soft tissue in Canal Wall Down (CWD) mastoidectomy demonstrates significant benefits over conventional methods. Postauricular soft tissue provides an effective barrier, promotes quicker and more effective healing, reduces inflammation and discharge, and enhances surgical outcomes. The future of mastoid cavity obliteration with postauricular soft tissue in canal wall down (CWD) mastoidectomy is likely to see several advancements and refinements aimed at improving patient outcomes, surgical efficiency, and overall healthcare effectiveness. Advances in endoscopic and minimally invasive surgical techniques could reduce surgical trauma, improve precision, and enhance recovery times. These techniques may allow for better visualization and access during surgery, leading to more effective obliteration and fewer complications. The use of post-auricular flaps helps achieve better outcomes. Still, developing new biomaterials that closely mimic natural tissue's properties could enhance mastoid cavity obliteration's success. This study helps in understanding the benefits of newer techniques compared to age-old traditional CWD mastoidectomy.

SUMMARY

The study “ To assess surgical outcome of mastoid cavity obliteration with postauricular soft tissue in canal wall down mastoidectomy ”

was done in BLDE(DU) Shri B M Patil Medical college, hospital and research centre, Vijayapura during the period of November 2021 to November 2023

The study aimed to evaluate the surgical outcomes of mastoid cavity obliteration using postauricular soft tissue in patients undergoing Canal Wall Down (CWD) mastoidectomy.

Participants:

- Total of 48 subjects with Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media (CSOM).
- Subjects divided equally into case and control groups.
- Mean age: 30.4 years (case group), 34.7 years (control group).
- Gender distribution: 23 females (48%) and 25 males (52%).

Methodology:

- Patients were evaluated for ear discharge and epithelization at 15, 45, and 90 days post-surgery using the Merchant et al. grading system for otorrhea.

Findings:

1. Ear Discharge:

- At day 15, 50% of case group subjects had no or minimal ear discharge compared to 20% in the control group.
- At day 45, 79% of case group subjects attained grade 0 ear discharge, while only 50% of control group subjects did.
- The postauricular soft tissue provides a barrier that prevents the entry of infectious agents, enhances drainage, promotes quicker healing, and reduces cavity size.

2. Gender and Healing Outcome:

- Male subjects: 66% in the control group had grade 3 ear discharge, compared to 6% in the case group.
- Female subjects: 63% in the case group attained grade 0 ear discharge by day 15, compared to 26% in the control group.
- Females showed better healing, potentially due to hormonal differences (e.g., estrogen enhancing collagen production, angiogenesis, and inflammatory responses).

3. Age and Healing Outcome:

- Younger age groups had better healing outcomes, with 100% of the case group attaining grade 0 ear discharge by day 45 compared to 90 days for the control group.
- Older patients showed slower healing due to reduced cellular regeneration, weaker immune responses, and more comorbidities.

4. Epithelization:

- At day 15, 33% of case group subjects had epithelization compared to 24% in the control group.
- At day 45 and 90, 63% and 88% of case group subjects had fully formed epithelial tissue compared to 38% and 54% in the control group.

Benefits of Postauricular Flap:

- Reduced chronic infections by sealing the mastoid cavity.
- Promoted better healing due to a rich blood supply.
- Minimized risk of rejection and complications.
- Provided durable and stable long-term results with fewer recurrences and revision surgeries needed.

Future Prospects:

- Advances in minimally invasive techniques.
- Development of new biomaterials mimicking natural tissue properties.
- Improved visualization and access during surgery.

This study highlights the effectiveness of using postauricular soft tissue for better surgical outcomes in CWD mastoidectomy, emphasizing the importance of gender and age in healing processes.

REFERENCES

1. Lasisi AO, Olaniyan FA, Muibi SA, Azeez IA, Abdulwasiu KG, Lasisi TJ, et al. Clinical and demographic risk factors associated with chronic suppurative otitis media. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol*. 2007 Oct;71(10):1549–54.
2. Kong K, Coates HLC. Natural history, definitions, risk factors and burden of otitis media. *Medical Journal of Australia*. 2009 Nov 2;191(S9).
3. Mathur N, Goyal LK, Badhaliya OP. Surgical outcome of mastoid cavity obliteration with postauricular soft tissue in canal wall down mastoidectomy. *European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine* [Internet]. 2021;8:925+. Available from: <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A698308164/HRCA?u=anon~9786389b&sid=googleScholar&xid=4f0ea06c>
4. Grote JJ, van Blitterswijk CA. Reconstruction of the Posterior Auditory Canal Wall with a Hydroxyapatite Prosthesis. *Annals of Otology, Rhinology & Laryngology*. 1986 Mar 4;95(2_suppl):6–9.
5. REIMER A, ANDREASSON L, HARRIS S. Surgical treatment of cholesteatoma: a comparison of closed and open techniques in a follow-up of 164 ears. *Clinical Otolaryngology*. 1987 Oct;12(6):447–54.
6. Frank H. Netter. *Atlas of Human Anatomy*. 2008;6.
7. Gerard J. Tortora BHD. *Principles of Anatomy and Physiology*. 2008;
8. Paul W. Flint BHHVJLKTRJRTMMLHWF. *Cummings Otolaryngology*. 2020;3(7).
9. Kennedy KL LJ. *Mastoidectomy*. 2023 May;
10. Mocanu H, Mocanu AI, Bonciu A, Coadă G, Schipor MA, Rădulescu M. Analysis of long-term functional results of radical mastoidectomy. *Exp Ther Med*. 2021 Aug 26;22(5):1216.
11. Das C, Hazra TK. Relook on Mastoid Cavity Obliteration: A Prospective Study. *Indian Journal of Otolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery*. 2019 Nov 5;71(S2):1107–14.
12. Shah AK, Patel S, Pawde A. Surgical Outcome of Mastoid Cavity Obliteration Using Postauricular Composite Bone with Periosteum Flap. *Indian Journal of Otolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery*. 2019 Mar 28;71(1):115–9.
13. Wadhwa V, Anand TS, Kumar S, Kathuria G, Rana I. Periosteal-Temporo-fascial flap for cavity obliteration - first Indian study. *Indian Journal of Otolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery*. 2003 Jul;55(3):170–4.
14. Lucidi D, De Corso E, Paludetti G, Sergi B. Quality of life and functional results in canal wall down vs canal wall up mastoidectomy. *Acta Otorhinolaryngologica Italica*. 2019 Feb;39(1):53–60.

15. Hunter JB, OBP, RA, & WGB. Obliteration of the Mastoid Cavity with Hydroxyapatite Cement. *Otology & Neurotology*. 2006;27(3):344–50.
16. Shah AK, Patel S, Pawde A. Surgical Outcome of Mastoid Cavity Obliteration Using Postauricular Composite Bone with Periosteum Flap. *Indian Journal of Otolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery*. 2019 Mar 28;71(1):115–9.
17. KARAMERT R, ERAVCI FC, CEBECİ S, DÜZLÜ M, ZORLU ME, GÜLHAN N, et al. Canal wall down versus canal wall up surgeries in the treatment of middle ear cholesteatoma. *Turk J Med Sci*. 2019 Oct 24;49(5):1426–32.
18. Yusof ANM, Boon WJ, Ali A, Tang IP. Outcomes of canal wall down mastoidectomy in cholesteatoma: a 5-year experience. *The Egyptian Journal of Otolaryngology*. 2023 Mar 15;39(1):50.
19. Ashcroft GS, Mills SJ. Androgen receptor–mediated inhibition of cutaneous wound healing. *Journal of Clinical Investigation*. 2002 Sep 1;110(5):615–24.
20. Gilliver SC, Ashworth JJ, Ashcroft GS. The hormonal regulation of cutaneous wound healing. *Clin Dermatol*. 2007 Jan;25(1):56–62.
21. Kovats S. Estrogen receptors regulate innate immune cells and signaling pathways. *Cell Immunol*. 2015 Apr;294(2):63–9.
22. Mehta RP, Harris JP. Mastoid Obliteration. *Otolaryngol Clin North Am*. 2006 Dec;39(6):1129–42.
23. van Hövell tot Westerflier CVA, van Wijk MP, Kon M. Surgical Correction of the “Sunken Ear.” *Otolaryngology–Head and Neck Surgery*. 2016 Jun 3;154(6):1161–3.
24. Al-Rawashdeh B, Tawalbeh M. Mastoid cavity obliteration in CWD mastoidectomy with periosteal-pericranial flap: A 10-year experience. *Jordan Med J*. 2020 Jul;55:24–35.
25. Ishman SL, Stewart CM, Senser E, Stewart RW, Stanley J, Stierer KD, et al. Qualitative synthesis and systematic review of otolaryngology in undergraduate medical education. *Laryngoscope*. 2015 Dec;125(12):2695–708.

ANNEXURE- I ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

BLDE

(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Declared as Deemed to be University u/s 3 of UGC Act, 1956

Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC (Cycle-2)

The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 707/2022-23

30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on **Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m. in the Department of Pharmacology** scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "SURGICAL OUTCOME OF MASTOID CAVITY OBLITERATION WITH POSTAURICULAR SOFT TISSUE IN CANAL WALL DOWN MASTOIDECTOMY".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: Dr. Justin Sebastian

NAME OF THE GUIDE : Dr. R. N. Karadi, Professor, Dept. of ENT.

Dr. Santoshkumar Jeevangi
Chairperson
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
Chairman,

**Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)**

Vijayapura

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutinization,

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Dr. Akram A. Naikwadi
Member Secretary
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA

MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethics Committee
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
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ANNEXURE-II
PROFORMA
SCHEME OF CASE TAKING

- | | |
|--|----------|
| 1) NAME: | CASE NO: |
| 2) AGE: | IP NO: |
| 3) SEX: | DOA: |
| 4) RELIGION: | DOS: |
| 5) OCCUPATION: | DOD: |
| 6) RESIDENCE: | |
| 7) CHIEF COMPLAINTS: | |
| 8) HISTORY OF PRESENTING ILLNESS: | |
| 9) PAST HISTORY: | |
| 10) FAMILY HISTORY: | |
| 11) GENERAL PHYSICAL EXAMINATION: | |
| 12) VITALS PR BP WT | |
| 13) OTHER SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION: | |
| 14) LOCAL EXAMINATION | |

VARIABLE	DAY 15	DAY45	DAY 90
EAR DISCHARGE			
EPITHELISATION			

ANNEXURE-III
INFORMED CONSENT FORM

BLDE (Deemed to be university) SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE
HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA- 586103

TITLE OF THE PROJECT

“To assess surgical outcome of mastoid cavity obliteration with postauricular soft tissue in canal wall down mastoidectomy ”

PG STUDENT

- Dr. JUSTIN SEBASTIAN

DEPARTMENT OF
OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

PG GUIDE

- Dr. R.N.KARADI
PROFESSOR AND HOD
DEPARTMENT OF
OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE
HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE,
VIJAYAPUR, KARNATAKA– 586103

All aspects of this consent form are explained to the patient in the language understood by him/her.

1) PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

I have been informed about this study. I have also been given a free choice of participation in this study.

2) PROCEDURE:

I am aware that in addition to routine care received I will be asked series of questions by the investigator. I have been asked to undergo the necessary investigations and treatment, which will help the investigator in this study

3) RISK AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that I may experience some pain and discomfort during the examination or during my treatment. This is mainly the result of my condition and the procedure of this study is not expected to exaggerate these feelings that are associated with the usual course of treatment.

4) BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in this study will help to the patients survival and better outcome.

5) CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that the medical information produced by this study will become a part of Hospital records and will be subject to the confidentiality and privacy regulation. Information of a sensitive personal nature will not be a part of the medical records, but will be stored in the investigator's research file and identified only by a code number. The code-key connecting name to numbers will be kept in a separate location.

If the data are used for publication in the medical literature or for teaching purpose, no name will be used and other identifiers such as photographs and audio or videotapes will be used only with my special written permission. I understand that I may see the photographs and videotapes and hear the audiotapes before giving this permission.

6) REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may ask more questions about the study at anytime. DR. G.MOHAN RAAJ is available to answer my questions or concerns. I understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the course of the study, which might influence my continued participation.

If during the study, or later, I wish to discuss my participation in or concerns regarding this study with a person not directly involved, I am aware that the social worker of the hospital is available to talk with me. A copy of this consent form will be given to me to keep for careful reading.

7) REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice to my present or future care at this hospital. I also understand that DR. G.MOHAN RAAJ may terminate my participation in the study after he has explained the reasons for doing so and has helped arrange for my continued care by my own physician or physical therapist, if this is appropriate.

8) INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to me resulting directly from my participation in this study, if such injury were reported promptly, the appropriate treatment would be available to me, but no further compensation would be provided. I understand that by my agreement to participate in this study I am not waiving any of my legal rights.

I have explained to _____ the purpose of the research, the procedures required and the possible risks and benefits to the best of my ability in patient’s own language.

Dr. JUSTIN SEBASTIAN

Date

(Investigator)

STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT

I confirm that Dr. JUSTIN SEBASTIAN has explained to me the purpose of research, the study procedures that I will undergo, and the possible risks and discomforts as well as benefits that I may experience in my own language.

I have read and I understand this consent form. Therefore, I agree to give consent to participate as a subject in this research project.

Participant / Guardian

Date

Witness to signature

Date

ANNEXURE-IV MASTERCHART

S.No	NAME	AGE CATEGORY	AGE	SEX	UHID NO	EAR DISCHARGE DAY 15	EPITHELIALISATION DAY 15	EAR DISCHARGE DAY 45	EPITHELIALISATION DAY 45	EAR DISCHARGE DAY 90	EPITHELIALISATION DAY 90	CASE GROUP
1	lohit	18-35		20 m	137299		0 yes		0 yes		0 yes	
2	prateeksha	<18		6 f	134347		0 yes		0 yes		0 yes	
3	shrushti	<18		17 f	191005		0 yes		0 yes		0 yes	
4	nikitha	<18		13 f	302794		0 yes		0 yes		0 yes	
5	sudeep chawan	<18		16 m	173549		0 no		0 no		0 yes	
6	basavaraj dhareppa	>50		57 m	24520		0 yes		0 yes		0 yes	
7	venkappa	>50		72 m	2213		3 no		3 no		3 no	
8	bismilla	36-50		39 f	20046		2 no		0 yes		0 yes	
9	aravind	>50		53 m	427540		0 no		0 no		0 yes	
10	sachin	18-35		23 m	17452		1 no		0 yes		0 yes	
11	rajesh	36-50		40 m	31242		1 no		0 yes		0 yes	
12	vinod	18-35		32 m	27214		0 yes		0 yes		0 yes	
13	adarsh	<18		12 m	18843		1 no		0 no		0 yes	
14	ganesh chidanand	<18		15 m	20723		1 no		0 yes		0 yes	
15	shrimanth	>50		62 m	350340		2 no		1 no		0 yes	
16	pooja	18-35		20 f	44879		1 no		0 yes		0 yes	
17	kallappa	36-50		44 m	37271		1 no		0 yes		0 yes	
18	dayanand	36-50		38 m	16965		2 no		1 no		0 yes	
19	ishwar	36-50		46 m	354086		0 no		0 no		0 yes	
20	somarraya	18-35		22 m	140678		0 yes		0 yes		0 yes	
21	sachin	18-35		18 m	324510		2 no		1 no		1 no	
22	darshana	<18		6 f	27653		0 no		0 yes		0 yes	
23	santrupti	<18		9 f	362089		0 yes		0 yes		0 yes	
24	ratnamma	>50		51 f	31458		3 no		2 no		1 no	
30.45833												

S.No	NAME	AGE CATEGORY	AGE	SEX	UHID NO	EAR DISCHARGE DAY 15	EPITHELIALISATION ON DAY 15	EAR DISCHARGE DAY 45	EPITHELIALISATION DAY 45	EAR DISCHARGE DAY 90	EPITHELIALISATION DAY 90	CONTROL GROUP
1	yamanappagouda	36-50		47 m	406446		3 no		1 no		0 no	
2	nirmala	18-35		35 f	10228		2 no		0 yes		0 yes	
3	nagaraj	36-50		36 m	382954		3 no		2 no		2 no	
4	shantayya	36-50		38 f	270942		2 no		0 no		0 yes	
5	laxmi ningappa	18-35		29 f	378480		0 no		0 yes		0 yes	
6	kenchappa	<18		14 m	40651		1 no		0 yes		0 yes	
7	keshav pattar	>50		52 m	382956		2 no		0 no		0 yes	
8	sraavan	>50		57 m	354988		3 no		3 no		3 no	
9	kartik narasappa	<18		10 m	146119		3 no		2 no		1 no	
10	pavitraraj bannur	18-35		24 f	285754		0 no		0 yes		0 yes	
11	kalyan kumar	18-35		19 m	332448		0 yes		0 yes		0 yes	
12	rukmalai sadav	36-50		42 f	206078		3 no		2 no		1 no	
13	rudramma	>50		55 f	365671		3 no		3 no		1 no	
14	parvathi	18-35		32 f	324108		0 no		0 yes		0 yes	
15	basavanthray	>50		75 m	291252		3 no		3 no		3 no	
16	neelamma	36-50		44 f	314117		2 no		2 no		0 no	
17	amruta ramaji	<18		11 f	321113		1 no		1 no		0 yes	
18	mahanandawwa	18-35		35 f	341568		1 no		0 yes		0 yes	
19	radhika	<18		12 f	284459		3 no		3 no		2 no	
20	parvati	18-35		26 f	311014		2 no		1 no		0 yes	
21	mallamma	18-35		30 f	309477		3 no		0 yes		0 yes	
22	gurupaddappa gouda	36-50		50 m	341136		3 no		2 no		1 no	
23	geetha	18-35		23 f	341427		1 no		0 yes		0 yes	
24	savitri	36-50		37 f	30461		0 no		0 no		0 no	
34.70833												

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Sl.No	Title	Name of Journal - Volume/
1	Isolated Uvulitis	I.J.Laryngol.,Otol. & HNS.
2	Mixed Laryngocoele: A rare cause for acute airway obstruction	International Journal of Biomedical And Advanced Research
3	A Study of Anatomical Variations of Osteomeatal Complex in Chronic Rhinosinusitis Patients-Ct Findings	JCDR
4	A Case of Intratonsillar Abscess Managed by Needle Aspiration	J. Evolution Med. Dent. Sci./ eISSN- 2278-4802, pISSN- 2278-4748
5	Situation and control of early hearing loss among below poverty line people in southern India	International Journal of Health Science Research
6	Foreign Bodies of Tracheo-bronchial tree: A Retrospective Study,	International Journal of Contemporary Medical Research 11/2016,Volume 3, Issue 11, Pages 3202-3204
7	Aberrant Thyroid in the Parapharyngeal Space	Bengal Journal of Otolaryngology and Head Neck Surgery
8	Antrochoanal Polyp Recurrence - free management : our experience	IJOL,10(1): 4-10,
9	Deep Neck space infection: an iceberg	IJOL
10	Vocal cord Lateralization in bilateral abductor paralysis by extra-endo laryngeal suture technique: a case series	Indian Journal of Otolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery

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